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San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

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DEVELOPMENT AND ACCEPTABILITY OF THE MODULE IN TECHNICAL DRAFTING IN SELECTED PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN THE DIVISION OF ANTIPOLO CITY

ARIEL MARGALLO DONSAI

Teacher III

Bagong Nayon Ii National High School

Region IV - A CALABARZON

TITLE: DEVELOPMENT AND ACCEPTABILITY OF THE MODULE IN TECHNICAL
DRAFTING IN SELECTED PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN THE DIVISION OF ANTIPOLO CITY

AUTHOR: **Ariel M. Donsal**

ADVISER: Dr. Bayani P. Paz

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NAME AND ADDRESS OF INSTITUTION: Tomas Claudio Colleges, Morong, Rizal

Methodology

Descriptive and Experimental Research

Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations

The study aimed to develop and determine the acceptability of a module in Technical Drafting in six selected public secondary schools in the Division of Antipolo City. The study was conducted during the school year 2016-2017.

There were two groups of respondents in the study, the sixty (60) teachers from each selected schools who are teaching TLE and the Grade 9 students who are divided in to two groups, the exposed and the unexposed. The Grade 9 students are comprised of fifty (50) students from Grade 9 Garnet and Grade 9 Sapphire. Sixty (60) teachers were described in terms of age, sex, position title, educational

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attainment, and length of service. They were also requested to determine the acceptability of the module with respect to objectives, contents, organization and presentation, language and style, evaluation, and usefulness.

Findings of the study included the following: Most teachers belong to the younger age range. They have been in the service for 1-5 years. The module was found to be Much Acceptable, having the following components, usefulness, content organization and presentation evaluation, language and style, and objectives. The hypothesis is accepted, as to level of performance in the pretest, all the 25 or 100 percent students both who are unexposed to the module and the exposed obtain scores in the range interpreted as Moderately Satisfactory. In the posttest, majority in both groups are still in the moderately satisfactory level, however, for the exposed group 32% move up to the satisfactory level as compares to 8% in the unexposed group. The hypothesis on the significant difference on the level of performance of the exposed in the pretest and posttest was rejected however it was accepted for the unexposed group. The hypothesis that there is a significant difference of the level of performance in Technical Drafting of the posttest was rejected.

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn: The teachers find the developed module in technical drafting much acceptable. The performance of the students exposed to the developed module in technical drafting is better than students' performance using traditional method. The developed module for technical drafting is effective in teaching drawing.

In the light of the findings, the following recommendations are hereby offered: The module may be reviewed to find out some parts which are needing adjustment and revision to make it more suitable and effective for the students, the module may be utilized in a longer duration after its revision to increase students' performance and may be conducted a parallel study using other variables be done.

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